

Horizon Europe Project PLANET4B

REPORT ON TRAINING FOR CASE STUDY FACILITATORS ON DEPLOYING METHODS

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

PLANET4B

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PLANET4B

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Definition
BCD	Behavioural Centred Design
BCF	Ben Cook Filmmaker
CG	CzechGlobe – Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences
CGE	Culture Goes Europe
CU	Coventry University
DC	Dadima's CIC.
ESSRG	Environmental Social Science Research Group
FiBL	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture
FUG	Forum Urban Gardening
GD	Good Issue Ltd.
IFZ	Interdisciplinary Research Centre for Technology, Work and Culture
MLU	Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg
NINA	Norwegian Institute for Nature Research
PLANET4B	understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making
Rare	Center for Behavior and the Environment
RU	Radboud University
UNEP-WCMC	UN Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre
UNIFI	University of Pisa
Work Package	WP
WUEB	Wroclaw University of Economics and Business

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Executive summary

- Halting or reversing biodiversity loss requires intervention methods that go beyond conventional (laws and regulations, markets and incentives, information) intervention methods.
- Creative, arts-based, deliberative methods promote conscious, intentional, reflexive change; attention, framing, and nudging experiments are particularly useful for shaping default choices and habitual change.
- Three intervention methods sets were explored, experienced, and analysed at the PLANET4B training for case study facilitators: creative, arts-based, deliberative; attention, framing, nudging experiments; experiential learning games and debriefing.
- The specific intervention methods included creative and participatory filmmaking, a collective and experimental shopping and cooking challenge, a behaviour-centred-design approach for achieving behaviour change, a newly developed biodiversity-food-governance game and debriefing.
- Thirty representatives from 18 organisations, including three additional experts specialised in one of the featured methods sets, participated in the training.
- Experiential learning games and debriefing tend to combine these two emphases of social change but are more resource intensive to implement.
- Overall, the case study facilitators found all three sets of the intervention methods useful, and the discussions generated further reflections confirming the suitability of the tested methods for biodiversity prioritisation.

1 Introduction to the training

One of PLANET4B's working hypotheses is that societies at all levels – individual, community, institutional – need transformative change in order to halt or reverse the alarming rates of biodiversity loss in equitable ways (D2.1). To address this need, PLANET4B has been working on intervention methods that go beyond traditional approaches (laws and regulations, markets and incentives, information) and can be piloted and implemented with the resources and capacities of the involved case study Learning Communities and their Stakeholder Boards (D3.1). This document reports on the training for case study facilitators for deploying the three sets of intervention methods: creative, arts-based, deliberative; attention, framing, nudging experiments; and experiential learning games and debriefing. The training that took place 17–19 January 2024 in Berlin, Germany, was attended by 27 representatives of the PLANET4B consortium from the organisations CG, CGE, CU, DC, ESSRG, FiBL, FUG, GD, IFZ, MLU, NINA, RU, UNEP-WCMC, UNIPi, as well as three additional experts (Rare, WUEB and BCF, respectively specialists in each of the methods sets selected for the training).

We continue by providing the project-related background to the training before reporting on the implementation of the three sets of intervention methods. We then highlight the key findings of the event and conclude with an outlook.

2 Three sets of intervention methods at the training

Over the course of the project, the PLANET4B consortium, particularly Task 2.1 of the project, has been conducting three different types of review: (1) review of the theories of behavioural and institutional change that could particularly be helpful to explain change or lack of it in the biodiversity domain (Task 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.4); (2) review of the context and needs in the case studies that focused on place- or sector-specific intersectionality dimensions, biodiversity problems, various intrapersonal, interpersonal, institutional barriers and opportunities for prioritising biodiversity in decision-making (D3.1); and (3) review of intervention methods: creative, arts-based, deliberative; attention, framing, nudging experiments; and experiential learning games and debriefing (conceptualised in Fig. 1, adapted from D2.1). Based on the iterative process where respective Task Leads learned from partners and continuously refined their review results, a training event was planned for month 15 of the project aimed at developing the capacities of case study facilitators for deploying the methods in their case study. The key objectives of the training were to gain hands-on experience with the key methods sets, have space for critical reflection about them, discuss their suitability/application in the case studies, and develop specific facilitation knowledge and skills. These key objectives have shaped the co-developed agenda of the training (see Annex) and the structure of this report. The following subsections explain briefly the idea of the methods sets in focus, the key activities carried out at the training, and conclusions specific to these methods sets. We then provide our key takeaways from this workshop and outlook.

Figure 1. Reflexivity-Contextualisation-Matrix (RCM). Source: Soliev et al. (2023).

2.1 Creative, arts-based, deliberative intervention methods

Methods from the social sciences and humanities, which encompass deliberative, creative, and arts-based approaches, present a promising avenue for fostering deeper public dialogue and individual as well as collective reflexivity. These methods offer a means to challenge assumptions that both individuals and societies all too often accept unquestioningly. Embracing socially inclusive research practices and acknowledging the value of diverse forms of knowledge, while remaining mindful of power dynamics and the intersections of social structures that perpetuate inequalities (Kaijser and Kronsell, 2014), such methods aim to facilitate the co-creation of new interpretations and insights into social-ecological relationships and vulnerabilities. This in turn has the potential to engender novel approaches to problem-solving and behaviour (Franklin, 2022). Individual examples of such creative, deliberative and arts-based methods include storytelling, guided poetry walks, immersive role-playing experiences and citizen juries, all of which encourage alternative and critically reflexive perspectives on

biodiversity¹. Where time and resources permit, sensitively combining a series of individual methods holds the possibility of deepening the impact of this method set on both participants and observers. Examples of methods which support the weaving together of two or more individual methods include participatory film making and public exhibition.

Day 1 of the Berlin workshop focused on immersively training consortium members in weaving together creative, arts-based, and deliberative interventions methods. The two principal methods used to co-ordinate and combine associated individual methods were participatory filmmaking and a collective and experimental shopping and cooking challenge.

Figure 2. Members of Team 3 of the collective and experimental shopping and cooking challenge on Day 1. Source: Authors' own work.

The idea of the participatory filmmaking activity arose primarily due to CU's previous experience in this area with [The Research Film Maker: Using Film in Research \(Online\) \(ncrm.ac.uk\)](http://ncrm.ac.uk). The workshop session could then be led by an "in house" filmmaking expert from within the CU team, in combination with an external expert (Ben Cook Filmmaker (BCF)). The idea of organising a collective and experimental shopping and cooking challenge arose primarily from discussions with the organiser CGE that has the experience and resources to provide the necessary conditions for this.

Combining the participatory filmmaking and the collective and experimental shopping and cooking challenge provided a method set to test. The aims of this were two-fold: on the one hand, to explore, experience and reflect on a creative challenge collaboratively with particular focus on decision-making about biodiversity, and; on the other hand, to document this challenge for a film as a basis for engaging in a dialogue about how we approach telling stories and how the medium of film can be used to facilitate, as well as promote, engagement and action (particularly how it can be used in PLANET4B to advocate for change).

¹ For a list of intervention methods (creative, arts-based, deliberative; attention, framing, nudging experiments; and experiential learning games and debriefing methods) identified by PLANET4B, please see [Directory of key methods most suitable for biodiversity decision-making contexts](#) (D2.1). The list is updated on an ongoing basis.

There is an increasing trend towards the use of film in research and data collection, impacting on different areas of research and even contributing to policy making in national research (Mannay, 2015). Against this background, the use of pictures and/or filmmaking was pre-discussed as a possible tool within creative methods, and initial ideas were presented (see Table 1).

Table 1. List of partners' broad ideas for using images and/or films as part of the creative methods in their case studies. Source: Authors' own work.

Partner	Case study	Use of pictures/films as part of creative methods
CGE	Urban youth, intersectionality and nature	Outdoor methods with (urban) occupants – murals to show (urban) empty spaces via controversial pictures.
DC	Opening nature and the outdoors to Black, Asian and ethnic minority communities	Use of films in minority ethnic communities to enable their stories and experiences to be recorded and shared in a participatory and inclusive way.
FiBL	Swiss attitudes towards agro-biodiversity	Picture and/or video presented by the farmer at the end of the interview to show the connection to biodiversity.
FUG/IFZ	City food for biodiversity and inclusion	Use of films to provide a forum for participants (women) to express themselves.
RU	Trade and global value chains	A photographer to document the fieldwork. The results are to be used for a discussion on the establishment of an agency.
UNIFI	From "ego" to "eco" system – biodiversity and fashion	Use of films to share with students.

A working session (“participatory filmmaking”) was jointly delivered by CU and BCF to train participants in terms of objectives, implementation and ethics following the maxim: “we are all creative.” The extent of participation was not predetermined, as it can take place at different levels (i.e. ranging from involvement in all or only a limited number of the components involved in creating a film – story boarding, directing, filming, being a subject of film, creating additional feature content, editing).

Figure 3. CU/BCF delivering the working session “participatory filmmaking” on Day 1. Source: Authors' own work.

Participatory filmmaking is collaborative; however, ethics in filmmaking require consents and need constant reflection (Wiles et al., 2012). Participants were asked to always consider during the filmmaking process how people would be involved and whether they would feel comfortable with this. They were reminded of the PLANET4B ethics and data management commitments and encouraged to consult with the Ethics Committee should they need any further information or advice in follow on from the training event.

A film can be made in many ways (e.g. through photography, a bluescreen, sound or animation) depending on the purpose and the audience (e.g. call to action, engaging people). Stories can also be told in different ways, depending on the reach and impact that it intends to achieve (e.g. using actors to narrate an event to avoid the involvement of vulnerable groups in favour of ethical issues to ensure anonymity). CU/BCF presented an example of how participatory filmmaking can be realised (showing a film about the "Walking Warriors" – a self-organised working group that gathers every Saturday morning for walks with participants freely documenting – in accordance with their own preferences – and sharing stories, photos, footage, audio, music, poetry and mixed media during the walk).

For the combined challenge of filmmaking and the collective and experimental shopping and cooking challenge 23 participants were divided into five teams (with 4–5 participants per team). Care was taken to ensure each group was as diverse as possible in terms of gender and age. In addition, no organisation was represented by more than one person per team. Each team received the same instructions (see Annex). The participants were provided with a fully equipped kitchen at the venue. The teams were tasked to:

1. Internally agree on roles within the respective team (e.g. budget holder, principal chef, sui chef, washer-up).
2. Decide upon the team dish, based on:
 - Available time and budget;
 - Any specified diet or cooking restrictions;
 - Producing a dish which is biodiversity-positive;

- Catering for 15 people;
 - Taking into account the cooking facilities of the venue.
3. Source ingredients and prepare a dish, ensuring that it is ready to eat by 7 p.m. prompt.
 4. Plan from the outset how to creatively document their experience, including if and how the need for consideration of biodiversity impacted their decision making (at least one contribution per team member, with at least three different creative mediums used per team).
 5. Creatively document the activities and associated thoughts, feelings, observation and dialogue of their respective team and make all of the material available to BCF by 8.45 a.m. of Day 2 of the training event.

Figure 4. Members of Team 2 of the collective and experimental shopping and cooking challenge on Day 1. Source: Authors' own work.

As an additional challenge, it was decided to provide the teams with a different budget (see Table 2) for their task to source ingredients. The idea behind this was to create an aspect of financial inequality among the teams. Each team was informed about the budget available to them but was not given any information about that of the others to minimise any bias towards certain purchasing decisions in this regard.

In presenting their prepared dishes each group provided a brief immediate account of the decision making behind their dish, including in relation to their budget and what impact this had (e.g. in terms of purchasing decisions in favour of more sustainable or higher quality products or dishes). This was then followed on Day 3 of the training event, with an extended session of reflection and debriefing.

Table 2. Teams of the collective and experimental shopping and cooking challenge. Source: Authors' own work.

Team No	Participant	Organisation	Team budget in EUR	Money spent in EUR	
1	Geraldine Brown	CU	110	103.49	
	Kármén Czett	ESSRG			
	Subash Ludhra	DC			
	Torsten Wähler	MLU			
2	Céire Booth	UNEP-WCMC	90	71.84	
	Geeta Ludhra	UNIFI			
	Pedro Navarro Gambin	DC			
	Barbara Smith	CU			
	Ilkhom Soliev	MLU			
3	Nargiza Khudaynazarova	CGE	80	77.59	
	Vinícius Mendes	RU			
	David Steinwender	IFZ			
	Agnes Zolyomi	UNEP-WCMC			
	Michał Pająk	WUEB			
4	Vladislav Artiukhov	CGE	75	68.63	
	Andreas Motschiunig	FUG			
	Ghezal Sabir	FiBL			
	Anna Schellroth	MLU			
5	Marta Bonetti	UNIFI	70	87.17	
	Rafal P. Chudy	NINA			
	Alex Franklin	CU			
	Sandra Karner	IFZ			
	Zafar Saydaliev	CGE			

The Day 3 tended reflection session began with a film premiere. The film was created and edited by BCF during Day 2 of the training event using a wide selection of the

material provided by each of the teams. In accompaniment to showing the film BCF explained and answered a series of associated questions from participants on the editorial choices he had made, as well as his overall impression on the choice and quality of the material the groups had provided him to work with.

In addition to reflecting on the experience of co-creatively documenting the collective and experimental shopping and cooking challenge and the extent to which the resulting film effectively conveyed what they had been hoping to capture and share, participants also engaged in a lively discussion about their individual and collective experiences of the challenge.

Outcomes of the reflections on the use of creative and arts-based methods in combination with participatory film making included suggestions for shorter, even 30-second, films; show the end products, add subtitles and the context in the form of an introduction, consider introducing a structure to guide the viewer (e.g. People, Place, Activity), consider including a simple background sound track to increase viewer effect; ensure all consenting film subjects have an opportunity to view, approve and/or request edits prior to any public release of the film.

2.2 Attention, framing, and nudging experiments

Attention, framing and nudging experiments considering various biases and activating social norms have been used to trigger changes also in terms of biodiversity (Balmford et al., 2021) to add on the impacts of traditional levers. To present on such cases and to talk about the so-called Behaviour-Centred Design (BCD), Sam Gray from Rare held a workshop on Day 2. He briefly introduced the main steps of the process (framing the challenge – identify core audience, target behaviour and large context; empathise – understand data regarding motivation, barriers and context; map – hypothesise about the motivations and barriers that are likely to increase the target behaviour; ideate – create a prioritised list of solutions; prototype – make a prototype of essential elements of behaviour solutions; test – test prototyped solutions and incorporate feedback; launch – plan and implement the solution; assess – measure the effectiveness and impact of the solution. During the main steps of the process Sam also provided exercises so participants could discuss how to frame the problem on a specific case study and how to hypothesise about the possible solutions considering the context. Sam also provided several examples to the participants where Rare used the BCD with success.

For instance, in their “Fish Forever in Mozambique” project, Rare issued photo ID cards and improved the formal registration process and regulation for fishers to better identify who the fisher was. Bringing the registrar to the communities counteracted the barrier of travel into registration offices from remote locations and gave recognition to the fishers who had registered. Material incentives were also provided through exchanging of fishing gear with replacement offers. Additional step-by-step instructions – training, materials, informational forums, meetings, communication about the desired behaviour and giving feedback – were provided via information cards on the desired behaviours.

Local mascots in the programme also triggered appreciation and pride in species-led conversation, triggering more care about specific animals. Other social influences that can contribute to pro-biodiversity behaviour included: making the desired behaviour

observable; publicly broadcast who has not engaged in the target behaviour; provide a way for people to show they are displaying the desired behaviour; encourage public commitments (e.g. public signing of agreements).

Figure 5. Training participants during the workshop delivered by Rare on Day 2. Source: Authors' own work.

Sam invited participants to take part in an upcoming meeting in February with the Center for Behavior and the Environment at Rare to pose any specific questions they may have regarding experiments in their own cases and directed them to browse more materials and cases on Rare's website (behavior.rare.org).

2.3 Interventions based on experiential games and debriefing

In the biodiversity domain where actions of individual actors are not easily linked to the consequences of these actions, it is a particular challenge to prioritise biodiversity, especially in the face of tangible and short-term individual benefits. Complexity of the resource system, where causal processes have difficulty of attribution and are lengthy, makes monitoring and control of any external measures very costly. Hence, internalisation of norms that improve prioritisation of biodiversity in decision making, despite the uncertainty inherent to complex systems, are particularly important for sustaining biodiversity. Experiential behavioural games have been increasingly discussed in the literature as a promising intervention method to facilitate internalisation of such norms through changes in mental models and social learning. Yet developing a game is both a theoretical and practical challenge on its own as decisions must be made on myriad features of a game that can influence its outcomes both within and beyond the game, ranging from those on game narrative and experience to those on game rules and importance of player attributes

(see Falk et al., 2023). As part of the training, we have tested a game designed to trigger change in mental models and norms in relation to biodiversity and agriculture, integrating dilemmas that occur between an individual and group, between various groups, and between the society as a whole and important issues such as biodiversity loss. Importantly the session also included a debriefing session to allow participants to review, process, debate their experiences in the game and therewith have an opportunity to transform these experiences into learning relevant for real-life action.

Figure 6. Training participants during the games session on Day 2. Source: Authors' own work.

Further, building on the example from the games session, we had a separate session dedicated to understanding the importance of debriefing. Here the focus was on why debriefing is important: its elements, and practicalities not to be underestimated. The session was largely motivated by the experiential learning theory (Kolb, 1984; Kolb and Kolb, 2008) that stresses how knowledge is created through the transformation of experience (Figure 2). It is in fact argued that debriefing is the most important point of learning from the use of games and simulations (Thatcher, 1990) although surprisingly underapplied and underreported (Crookall, 2011).

Figure 7. The Experiential Learning Cycle. Source: Kolb and Kolb (2008).

Important elements of debriefing include guiding participants through an experience and looking at the impact through recollections and reporting in a given time (Lederman, 1992). Participants experience, express, examine and explore going through different phases of the debriefing:

- 1) Systematic reflection and analysis
- 2) Intensification and personalisation
- 3) Generalisation and application

Beyond the theory, facilitators of games need to keep in mind practicalities for conducting a good debriefing. This can include the fact that debriefings can include informal discussions, while often the main questions need to be structured in advance. One could also conduct debriefing in the form of written reports and commentary on the experience, as well as in a form that mixes a written individual reflection with group discussion. It is recommended to have a logical but flexible order of topics with a focus on research questions; use comprehensible and relevant language, avoid leading questions, record “facesheet” information (name, age, gender, position, etc.); make yourself familiar with the participants, make sure you have a compelling answer for potential questions; get a reliable tape recorder and microphone (tested). It is also important to have a quiet setting and learn how to be a successful facilitator – be knowledgeable, structuring, clear, gentle, sensitive, open, steering, critical, remembering, interpreting (adapted from Bryman, 2016). Facilitators should also think of types of questions (e.g. tell us about, what do you mean by that, what happened next, etc.). When beginning and finishing it is important to have an introduction: thank people, outline format, ethical issues, demographic information and with closing remarks, thank people again, explain what happens to the data and if there are any follow up events. Perhaps most importantly, after thinking about both the theory and practicalities, the facilitators should reflect on the level of their involvement. This may differ but generally some balance is recommended – ask a small number of general questions allowing a free rein to participants, intervene when discussion is going off track, respond to potentially interesting points. A discussion is followed among the

participants about experiences and recommendations including the consideration of intercultural aspects, intersectionality, biases and managing emotions and conflicts. In addition to the original case study where the games were planned to be implemented (Urban Youth, intersectionality and nature – Germany), several other participants expressed interest in using this intervention method for their case studies or as part of their courses offered at the universities (e.g. Italy to support discussions about fashion and biodiversity, Austria to support discussions about food and biodiversity). The importance of debriefing as a method to transform experience into knowledge has been supported virtually by all participants.

3 Key takeaways from the training and outlook

The objectives of the training were to gain hands-on experience with the key methods sets, have space for critical reflection about them, discuss their suitability/application in the case studies, and develop specific facilitation knowledge and skills. The feedback has been very positive in terms of achieving these objectives. Most participants had positive feeling about the training using the words “great”, “happy” and “inspired”. Some comments reflecting the intensity of the training and expressed that they were “tired” or “challenged”. Further comments indicated that participants were “more equipped”, “ready to take action” or “invigorated”. A key point raised at the end of the training was that at least some of the partners needed to think and talk more about the details of implementation in the case studies. Relevant questions associated with how best to implement one or more of the method sets in their respective case studies (e.g. how to integrate surveys and interviews into the interventions) were discussed and where possible clarified on the spot. It was agreed that the decisions must be made within the next weeks, while further details will be continuously discussed within the next workshops of the project (e.g. systems mapping planned within intensive case studies in the next months, etc.), and/or bilaterally between the partners and coordination team.

Overall, to the best knowledge of the authors of this report, this was the first training focused on non-conventional social interventions in the biodiversity domain, inclusive of an intersectional lens. Both the organisers and the participants found it very informative, while continuously critically reflecting on each method, their fit for the individual case studies, potential risks and other limitations. The event reinforced the confidence of the project team that the lessons from the upcoming implementation of the interventions will be of high relevance for increasing knowledge, as well as practical “know-how”, on how biodiversity can be better prioritised in decision-making at multiple – from individual to institutional – levels.

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Statement on data availability

Data used to produce this report include documents sent by cases and shared with all project members via SharePoint. None of these data sources is publicly available since they include personal data from participants.

Statement on ethics

This report does include pictures from the workshop's participants of many of the case studies. According to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the European Union (EU), names of individuals are personal data. The necessary consent forms have been sent to all participants upon them agreeing to participate in the PLANET4B project, requesting them to sign an authorisation for their pictures to be included in this report. The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

Annex

List of participants

#	Participants	Institution
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4	Céire Booth	UNEP-WCMC
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10	Alex Franklin	CU
11	Sam Gray	Rare
12	Sandra Karner	IFZ
13	Nargiza Khudaynazarova	CGE
14	Geeta Ludhra	DC
15	Subash Ludhra	DC
16	Vinícius Mendes	RU
17	Viktória Monhor	GD
18	Andreas Motschiunig	FUG
19	Pedro Navarro Gambín	UNIFI
20	Patricia Ofori-Amanfo	CG
21	Michał Pająk	WUEB
22	Ammalia Podlaszewska	CGE
23	Ghezal Sabir	FiBL
24	Zafar Saydaliev	CGE
25	Anna Schellroth	MLU
26	Barbara Smith	CU
27	Ilkhom Soliev	MLU
28	David Steinwender	IFZ
29	Torsten Wähler	MLU
30	Agnes Zolyomi	UNEP-WCMC